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Attitudinal and Behavioural commitment of students whilst being supervised on their thesis writing. An Experiential learning study at St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu

Abstract: Attitudinal and Behavioural Commitment can have high impact on achievement of academic goals; it must be present in supervisors and the students. In this study, an experiential learning research was conducted to find the nurturing of Open Source Understanding (OSU) through the preconditioned nature of Close Source Understanding (CSU) that enables to enhance the students' level of commitment. Qualitative method was applied through open interview structured questions at two levels prior to the completion and post completion of report writings. Respondents were ten students and constant supervisions were carried out. Crystallization and triangulation analysis method were performed to analyse and interpret the data and giving meaning to it. Theoretical construction were designed with commitment theories and reflections of personality and styles/approaches were verified to arrive at this experiential learning study conducted at the St. Xavier's College, with Bachelor's Degree students. The findings suggest that commitment level changes are like the personality that changes in any adult. The results suggest that commitment can be nurtured but have the attributes of personality and styles. Among these two commitment OSU and CSU in students, CSU is grounded in behavioural attributes and directly connected to personality and has high flexibility stretch, whereas OSU is a mind-setting attribute which is time-bound and can be nurtured and can remain consistent. This creates a vibration between their attitudinal and behavioural commitments, which is the pivotal to enhance the Collision of Acceptance (CoA). Alike psychological paradigm, the personality can also have an immense impact on shaping their commitment level, which can be understood by the *Collision of Ignorance (CoI)* stage.

Keywords: Academic writing; qualitative analysis; commitment; experiential learning; personality crisis

Introductions

Commitment is highly important aspect of life to accomplish the goals of life. Generally, commitment levels are evaluated in business organization, however, commitment is highly important in academic and educational settings. But do all students have attitudinal commitment (Open source understanding (OSU)? Or they just have the behavioural commitment (Close source understanding (CSU)). Likewise, commitment

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must also be highly present in supervisors while supervising the students on their thesis. Supervisors must have all the necessary “*Skills, Ability, Knowledge, Competences and Intelligence*” (SAKCI) (Rajbhandari, 2019), which enables to generate a conversion of behavioural commitment (close source understanding) to attitudinal commitment (open source understanding), however, Menezes, Bastos, Duran, Velosa and Almeida (2015) conclude that attitudinal commitment and behavioural commitment are related to each other.

Things are changing and with the COVID-19 situation, it has changed dramatically during and after the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown. This impacted the world economy, politics, social, psychology, education so on and so forth. This also changed the students’ commitment level while pursuing online classes lectures from home. This situation has changed the perspectives of behavioural pattern.

The COVID-19 pandemic situation created multiple problems that affected the livelihood of people and organizations brought up by economic pandemic (Rajbhandari, 2020a, 2020b) all around the world and education was also not spared at all which was hit to suffer the most by all age groups. Despite such situation, many schools, colleges and universities offered online classes to continue their educational realm. However, things didn’t remain the same as before and thus people moved towards adopting the New Normal 2020 situation.

The New Normal during this COVID-19 pandemic changed the lives of all affecting the internal environment caused by the external environment. Nevertheless, the race against the odds were on-going and after many months of attempted adaptation, the situation became familiar to all by learning to live with the changes that was brought about by this 2020 pandemic. Even within the challenging situations, educational sectors were continuously offering their educational services to all age groups through the introduction of technologies such as that of online classes. Things came into stabilizing as the New Normal 2020 (Hermann, 2020) which was perceived as a familiar situation as before. This led many educational sectors to reopen its normal face to face teaching and so on the schools, colleges and universities opened its normal activities while measures were taken into consideration to prevent COVID-19 to spread. As time went by, the new variant was discovered which was spreading from the United Kingdom named as *B117* (Crains, 2021) also called variant of concern (Ball, 2021) a multiple time faster spreading virus than COVID-19. However, due to the introduction of vaccines the situation was under control but few countries within UK went into lockdown yet again.

In the case of Nepal, the B117 was not known and the New Normal 2020 situation was coming back to normal especially within business and educational sectors. During this time after a prolonged lockdown and online classes, the face to face (physical) education started to take a normal shape. The educational boards announced the examination dates, the enrolments were restarted for the fresher’s and the public schools were also reopening. Nevertheless, it was difficult to measure the commitment level of the students.

Consequently, commitment levels of individuals are affected by both the internal as well as external environs. Moreover, internal environment are highly affected by the external forces. This forces can create agitation within the micro climate and thus brings the vibrations in the commitment level in individuals, groups within an organization. This can further affect the personality, styles and the behavioural pattern of

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any individuals, moreover, decreasing the commitment level, which further can cause the mirror effect (Rajbhandari 2015) that further can instigate to change the behavioural pattern of others. These changes of behavioural pattern, personality and styles can therefore impact on individuals' commitment level.

Theoretical construct

In this study, theoretical construct is within the study of commitment level of students while pursuing report writing. The commitment level is studied in to tier the attitudinal (OSU) and the Behavioural (CSU) commitments. It is assumed that attitudinal commitment (OSU) increase and the behavioural commitment (CSU) decreases overtime. During this stage of increase and decrease trend of these commitment levels, the understanding point between the supervisors and students is the Collision of Acceptance (CoA). This stage of CoA is important for the stagnant enhancement of attitudinal (OSU) commitment.

Figure 1 Theoretical construction of commitment of students towards the process of thesis writings

The above figure 1 of theoretical construction is a conceptualized theoretical perspective on the attitudinal commitment and behavioural commitment of students prior to starting to write the thesis and towards approaching to the end of completing their thesis writing. During this academic journey of writing thesis, many students approach their supervisors with their High on behavioural commitment (CSU) and low on attitudinal commitment (OSU). At a point where the real writing journey begins, the students will come to know and understand the technical aspects of academic writings and then their commitment level fluctuates. There is a state of collision when the supervisors and students level of understanding matches and both of theirs thinking Collide of Acceptance (CoA) level. Regardless of all such understanding prior to and during the pursuit of the academic writing journey, the students' understanding tend to be High on open source understanding (OSU) which is attitudinal commitment and low on closed source understanding (CSU) which is behavioural commitment.

Commitment can have various forms, Rajbhandari (2013) indicates commitment is multi-faceted. Maigo and Yan (2010) argue that commitment and effort are the two indicators that define motivation. Mowday, Steers, and Porter (1982), indicate two types of commitment, the attitudinal commitment as a mind-set of creating values and the behavioural commitment as dealing with the situational context in a contextual settings. In both these commitment paradigm plays a vital role in shaping individuals' motivational level while an attitudinal commitment is an Open sources of understanding (OSU) and the behavioural commitment is a Closed source of understanding (CSU) to increase the efficiency level of motivation.

For me, I resumed my office but the hours were flexible and not particularly structured as the normal college days. During this time, since the educational board announced the examination date for both thesis (report) submissions and paper exams, the students rolled in hustling towards the completion of their final report thesis. I was assigned ten students of bachelor's degree and the timeframe for the completion of their report (thesis) was only 16 days. Normally, the timeframe for submission of final report is 40 days but due to the pandemic, everything laid back except the policies that remained unchanged for all students as well as the supervisors who were assigned with students for supervising the thesis report.

Supervising 10 bachelors' level students was exciting, however, the time duration was not sufficient unless the reports were to be not of international quality standard. I started working with my ten students with the work they had written. According to the Educational Board, students were asked to write on three chapters, 1) Introduction, 2) Results/Analysis and 3) Summary and Conclusions. It was not to my surprise that all students were equipped with the knowledge about writing the report/thesis as a part of their academic degree. Moreover, all the students that were assigned to me were new students to me and I was new to them since we did not have any form of classroom interaction prior to this project.

The difficulties were faced from both sides, from the students and from my side. The first time we met face to face was when we organized the meeting session two days later after I was assigned with these ten students. My instruction was clear and simple, "I can help you only - if you work effectively". It was then agreed by all to follow the planned rules.

Knowing the supervisors

This was one of the toughest episodes on the students towards academic integration. Excitement was high on one part where as distress could be another. This could be due to the commitment level of both the supervisors and the students. However, both the commitment paradigm open source understanding and the close source understanding could be determined by the level of effort both the supervisors and the students puts in together to develop a quality academic standard report thesis that would eventually contribute towards education.

My experiential learning during this supervision was to generate open source understanding which can also be called as attitudinal commitment. However, the students I had for supervising their thesis had closed sources understanding. This then further generated mis-match between the students and supervision

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paradigm. Thesis supervision is not similar to teaching in the classroom where the environment of teaching and learning can be generated overtime within the timeframe to create harmony between the contextual framework and the lesson plan. For supervising my students and to create an open source understanding within them, rigorous face to face meet up discussion had to be initiated. This, therefore enabled me to understand the perceived value of my 10 students towards thesis report writing.

Gradually, the open source of understanding within the students was increasing and their closed source understanding decreased. This was the state of collision of acceptance level matched between me and my 10 students. However, there were two students who did not appear in the first lecture of induction lesson which made them follow their instinct to follow their behavioural commitment (CSU). This led them backward rather than towards moving forward. For me to reach the collision of acceptance level with these two students, addition discussions classes had to be conducted on face to face basis to regenerate the vibes to create the value towards their writing academic reports/thesis.

Although, simple it may be, it can equally be very difficult to pursue towards the collision of acceptance level. This requires both intensive and extensive “*Skills, Ability, Knowledge, Competences and Intelligence*” (SAKCI) (Rajbhandari, 2019) towards providing the adequate information on academic writing.

Methodology

The methodology for this study was conducted through the qualitative analysis. Crystallization method was used for analysis purpose. The crystallization method enabled me to capture the pieces of data and form into one common understanding. In addition to this, data triangulation was also used to validate the reliability of data during the analysis stages.

An open ended interview tool was used to collect the primary data from the 10 students. An interview schedule was designed for the respondents to answer the interview questions. The respondents included both genders and were given equal opportunity to answer the interview questions. The open ended interview was conducted at St. Xavier’s College premises with the 10 students. The respondents’ names are kept confidential and pseudonyms are used to identify and reflect their responses in a qualitative meaning.

For the purpose of interview, consents were taken from the respondents and the responses are organized for conducting the study for academic purpose alone.

Findings and Discussions

Commitment in any form may not always be beneficial and advantageous to the organization and the individual demonstrating such behaviours. This is because commitment can have various forms. Few of these formation of commitment are the attitudinal and behavioural commitment (Mowday, Steers and Porter, 1982), affective, normative, and continuance commitment (Meyers and Allen, 1997), while other forms of commitment could be Open Source Understanding (OSU) (value based) and Closed Source Understanding (CSU) (behavioural based) commitments. However, in this study, these forms of commitments are taken into

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inter-exchangeability to illustrate the similar common understanding of commitment levels amongst the students.

Figure 2 Commitment of students after completions of thesis writings

During this experiential learning research on the supervision of students at the St. Xavier's College for their bachelor's degree thesis writing, the commitment level on both the aspects open source understanding and the closed source understanding could be brought to collision of acceptance through the knowledgeable guidance by providing scientific approach towards writing and resolving the personality crisis (Rajbhandari, 2018). Personality crisis is the extreme fluctuating level of style-flex without having stagnancy in fixing the personal style drift (Rajbhandari, 2018). The personality must be stagnant to style-fixed on both supervisors and the students during the phase of writing report. This enables to generate the open source understanding (attitudinal commitment) level amongst the students and enable to decrease the close source understanding) behavioural commitment level. In early studies, researchers indicated that personality is stagnant and do not change in adults and claims that personality cannot have multi-functional style-flex (Mroczek & Spiro, 2003; Roberts, Walton, & Viechtbauer, 2006; Srivastava, et al., 2003). In recent studies, Robert and Mroczek (2008) suggest indicating that personality continues to change substantially and consequently in adults and in the old age.

Although both open source and close source understand levels are contributable factors, however, open source understanding is essential to generate the values of work and working together to arrive at the end results of completions of thesis writing. The open source understanding can be created by planning, organizing, controlling and communicating. These management functions have very important role in shaping the behavioural pattern of the students. This can further generate a vibe of academic disciplines amongst the students as the students have the tendencies of sharing matters among the friends circle. Shrestha, Sherpa, Rai and Malla (2019) illustrates that managerial functions enables to provoke organizational operations towards long run sustainability, which builds unique interpersonal relationships by creating an ethical working environment among people within and outside the organization.

Organizing towards achieving academic disciplines is a crucial part and lies completely in the hands of the supervisors. The organizing can involve many aspects such as, timing, scientific guideline, meet up

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discussions sessions with arguments etc. to name a few. Supporting this, all 10 respondents share their views by stating;

Table 1 Respondents view organizing and planning towards supervision

Respondent 1	“Yes, it was easy access for me to contact my supervision, the discussion meet up was well organized and it was helpful for me to develop the questionnaire with the help of my supervisor”.
Respondent 2	“Yes, it was well organized as each of us got equal chance to interact with our supervisor. For the questionnaire, It was prepared as per the instruction given by my supervisor, and yes, It was very easy to access to my supervisor”.
Respondent 3	“Yes, the access to contact our supervisor was easy. Yes, the discussion meet-up was organized. The discussion meet-up session on developing the questionnaire was good”.
Respondent 4	“The access was very convenient. Respected supervisor invested both his time and effort to guide us through the whole session. The discussion meet up was very well organized. The discussion meet up helped me to develop the questionnaire appropriately with the help of my supervisor”.
Respondent 5	“It was very easy as he was available on phone and also on <u>yiber</u> group. It was properly organized and it was very effective”.
Respondent 6	“Yes definitely access to my supervisor was very easy. He provided a very flexible time to meet and contact him and it was very organized and it was very interactive. During this meet up sessions very productive questions were developed”.
Respondent 7	“Yes the discussions meet up was very organized. Good, It was helpful in developing the questionnaire”.
Respondent 8	“Yes it was easy to contact my supervisor. Yes it was organized and was very helpful. It was very effective as our supervisor help us on making our questionnaire to related topic”.
Respondent 9	“Yes, it was easy to contact my supervisor. We were allowed to contact him anytime while we needed his supervision/guidance. Yes, it was organized. He gave us the time to visit, collect data and work on report. It was effective, as we sat with our supervisor for an hour and discussed relating to the topic and made a set of questionnaire. He even checked our <u>grammatical errors</u> ”.
Respondent 10	“Yes, the access to contact my supervisor was very easy as he was available via email, phone and meet up at any given time. Yes, the discussion meet up was very organized. The meet up session on developing the questionnaire was the key to conduct this report in a systematic and proper way”.

Nevertheless, organizing various factors during different stages can essentially generate the open source understanding (Attitudinal commitment) while progressively discarding the close source understanding (Behavioural commitment) within the students commitment level. Although behavioural commitment (close source understanding) can have immense impact in shaping the commitment level but without the attitudinal commitment (Open source understanding) it would be difficult for anyone to reach to the final destination.

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The attitudinal commitment (Open source understanding) must also be present in the supervisors therefore the collision of acceptance could be reached.

The collision of acceptance is highly essential and it may vary from one student to another, therefore, a supervisor may have multiple collision of acceptance while dealing with number of supervising students. Sometimes, a supervisor can have 10 collision of acceptance with ten different individual students or less.

Collision of acceptance stage is the meet point of understanding between the supervisor and the students, from which the attitudinal commitment (OSU) comes into shape and this is very important to generate among the students. Supporting this, the respondents' views are as follows, for which they state to answer on the questions asked and had various ways to defining to shape the OSU (attitudinal commitment).

Table 2 What was your thought before writing the report? (Opinion before assigning of supervisor and before we had classroom lecture on 3rd Jan 2021)

Respondent 1	"I was lost, as I did not know how to follow my research work".
Respondent 2	"I was absent".
Respondent 3	"I thought it will be easy and simple".
Respondent 4	"I was very sceptical as this was the very first time that I was going to conduct a research".
Respondent 5	"I had a huge misconception that report was something that was written with little information's but after the classroom lecture I got to understand the importance of writing report for the final year".
Respondent 6	"I was very nervous regarding my report writing; was not being able to figure out how to start the report. I was very confused".
Respondent 7	"I was in a state of confusion as this was my first report writing".
Respondent 8	"I thought it was easy to write a report. We can do it in a day".
Respondent 9	"I thought it would be easier we will be writing the report and after the submission we will complete our bachelors. I have heard it from my seniors that it will be very difficult but never did my report writing myself".
Respondent 10	"The report was solely based upon completing our fourth year examinations as a part of our research subject. A lot of classes were missed regarding the research report due to the Covid-19 pandemic and not a lot of guidance was provided. There was also very less time frame that we were provided to complete the report".

Table 3 How did you feel before (prior supervision) and how do you feel now (during and after supervision)?

Respondent 1	"Though I had theory knowledge regarding research project, I did not know how to put it on practice after supervision I was well directed and with the help of instruction i can properly implement the research work".
Respondent 2	"Before I was totally unaware about the proper step that needs to be followed up during report writing but during the process I felt the importance of time management and effective learning".
Respondent 3	"Before supervision I was unknown about the steps and topic to be followed in research writing process. During the session it was quite difficult to follow instruction and guidance of supervisor due to lack of limited knowledge about research and limited time. After supervision now I am being able to know about research and its method. Now through this work i can easily guide other in report writing process".
Respondent 4	"To be honest, I was quite lost as I had zero practicality in this field prior to supervision. After the supervision of my supervisor, i am much more confident and have learned the importance of research".
Respondent 5	"I was confused with the thesis before, now I am a bit confident on what to present on the work after the supervision".
Respondent 6	"Before I was confused and nervous regarding how will i finish my report. During the supervision period he provided me a right track to follow and conduct my research work and finally i am very thankful to my supervisor who invested his valuable time and effort on my research his constant motivation kept me motivated. Thank you so much for your support".
Respondent 7	"Before supervision I was confused and not sure from where to begin my research, and after supervision I got to know how to prepare a research report step by step".
Respondent 8	"I feel little bit nervous and scared about how will be my supervisor but after we met for first time at time also I feel a bit nervous but later I thought I can do it with the help of your guideline".
Respondent 9	"I was very scared how will my supervisor be? and now I am thankful for your guidance and support . Before the supervision I thought how will I do report? I don't know anything about but when we had our first lecture I felt like yes I can do.. And I did it all thanks to you sir. Thank you for every hour you guided me. It wouldn't have been possible without your guidance".
Respondent 10	"Before I had no knowledge on how a research report is prepared as I had only studied about it theoretically. After being a researcher to complete this report I learned a great deal of things. So I would like to thank my supervisor for helping me with this report through his continuous guidance and support".

For the open source understanding to take its shape within the students' mind-set, organizing, planning, controlling and communication is required while it is played on with supervisors' leadership towards formation of organized groups. For maintenance of leadership *art obstinate action* is required for teaching with why and how method rather than *science obstinate actions* of teaching with what method (Rajbhandari, 2018). He further explains the importance of art obstinacy actions by stating, "*the art-obstinate action* stipulates that the *leadership fix* generates a conducive climate for the leaders. Moreover, as followership domain is concern, fixing of followership towards the leader's conducive climate is also stipulated by the *art-obstinate action*; thus, generating a dominant leadership style by taking over control of the situation and followership domain" (Rajbhandari, 2018, 24; 2017).

Moreover, the art obstinate actions provide significant method towards staging a group formation towards increasing the open source understanding (attitudinal commitment) through Forming (coming together and

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becoming orientated), storming (power struggle and conflict resolution), norming (development of cohesiveness and open exchange), performing (in highly productive cooperation towards common goals) and adjourning (termination of the group) (Tuckman and Jensen 1977). This is further initiated by controlling and communication aspects which can be a pivotal aspect of leadership and followership integrating mechanism domain.

During the session of report writing, students were given instruction with proper illustration of following the writing method. This assimilated the communication and controlling mechanism to put together the students group to generate the open source understanding level. In this connection, the students replied while they were asked to answers on the questions as below:

Table 4 How was your experience while having face to face discussions on write up of 1st Chapter?

Respondent 1	"The lecture was very helpful. It guided me to fulfil my research work and It was informative".
Respondent 2	"It was two way of communication where I tried my best to follow up the instructions given by my supervisor. In my case Face to face discussion was the fastest way of learning and it was very helpful".
Respondent 3	"Firstly I was nervous to discuss about my topic because my proposal was so bad. Then our supervisor gave us proper guidance towards our chapter and topic. This made a fruitful experience while having face to face discussion on write up of 1st Chapter".
Respondent 4	"As mentioned above, the cloud of doubt was penetrated after the first face to face discussion session with the supervisor, and you guided us hand in hand and helped us to complete the chapters".
Respondent 5	"Since it was my first meet up with my supervisor I was really keen on learning. He guided me properly and amended my writings, also corrected my mistakes and taught me to write questionnaire and do surveys with the participants. We had one and half hour long consultation where I learned many things".
Respondent 6	"It was really fruitful. My respected supervisor, he is one of the best guides who helped me throughout my whole research work. The confusion and the nervousness before i started my research were gone and helped me develop confident to continue my work".
Respondent 7	"It was good. It was helpful too, because the discussion cleared many confusing matters that I had before".
Respondent 8	"The face to face discussion was far better then I thought. My supervisor gives his best to everyone's report writing which is very helpful for me as well my other friends".
Respondent 9	"After the classroom lecture on 3 rd Jan my supervisor immediately helped me and guided me after the lecture. And his guidance made me felt like did I really did my 1 st chapter on my own? It was unbelievable".
Respondent 10	"The experience was good as it was something where I had never been a part of. It was a challenge to do this report and it was first of many experiences where I learned how and what to include in my report. The guidance and instructions were very clear and to the point".

Table 5 Was it difficult for you all to follow up on my instructions?

Respondent 1	“No it was not difficult to follow up with the instruction you provided”.
Respondent 2	“It was quite difficult during my first chapter but after the meet up session eventually my performance got a lot better than I had expected”.
Respondent 3	“Yes, your instruction was very tough for me”.
Respondent 4	“It was rather easy to follow up on the instruction put forward by the supervisor as it was clear and to the point”.
Respondent 5	“Yes, it was kind of tough like I mentioned earlier as it was my first report”.
Respondent 6	“In fact Supervisor, advice and instruction made easy to conduct the research work. He motivated me thought my whole research work”.
Respondent 7	“No. As we had proper discussion before performing every step, the instructions were quite clear”.
Respondent 8	“In my opinion it is a bit tough maybe it is our first time to write a report in this way”.
Respondent 9	“Yes, your instruction was very tough for me to follow. So, I am about to complete the thesis bit earlier”.
Respondent 10	“The instructions were very clear and thorough. It was easy to understand and follow through the instructions”.

Moreover, to regenerate the open source understanding and keep it on a constant level for the consistency of academic persuasion motivation and constant support from the supervisors is also required. This generates the harmonious academic relationship amongst and between the supervisors and the students. Most often, students lack these commitments despite having been advised to develop adequate harmonious relations with their supervisors. These tendencies are not fatal but they can be instigating the close source understanding towards suppressing the open source understanding. Although, multiple attempts are being made towards the growth of open source understanding, it can be impossible to secure the 100% open source understanding from the students, this is because of the human nature as it is complex and changes accordingly.

However, in this study of experimenting on the open source understanding (attitudinal Commitment) to maintain constant, post-feedback was intentionally designed to seek feedback and comments from these 10

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students after the submission of final report. It was found that attitudinal commitment (open source understanding) is a time-bound commitment level that is generated and regenerated during the timeline of any project towards accomplishment of certain goals. Once the goal is achieved, the attitudinal commitment (open source understanding) can remain constant but the behavioural commitment (close source understanding) take over again, therefore, the behavioural commitment are instigated to grow towards the previous level which is prior to the start of any report writing projects.

It can thus be explained that behavioural commitment (Close source understanding) is closely connected with the individual's personality and their styles. However, attitudinal commitment (Open Source understanding) is a furnished and polishing a style and moulds the studenys' personality to meet the level of open source understanding with their supervisors.

It can also be interpreted that close source understanding (behavioural commitment) is grounded with the personality of mental understanding, while the physical side of personality can be attitudinal commitment (Open source understanding) and may not impact to decrease. Personality of an individual varies and has multi-faceted paradigm attached with both mental and physical attributes to demonstrate their individuals behaviour towards shaping their individuals styles.

To explain this, intended post feedback from the students were taken by asking them two questions:

1. *Could you share your opinion with regard to the experiences, support, feedback you received from your supervisors during the report writing?*
2. *Your opinion to other students*

For the attempt to understand the students open source understanding (attitudinal commitment) questions were sent through email for the students to answer. Among the 10 students who were supervised, only five replied to the questions and it wasn't made mandatory. The respondents who answered to these questions had different ways to express their thoughts and could relate to the consistency of attitudinal commitment (Open Source Understanding).

However, this cannot be interpreted that their behavioural commitment (Close source understanding) has decreased and the attitudinal commitment (Open source understanding) level has increased. It can only be interpreted that open source understanding (attitudinal commitment) have shaped a constant level of commitment, which was not found prior to the supervision and report writings. In connection to this and to support with the open source understanding (attitudinal commitment), the 5 respondents stated for the post feedback.

Table 6 Post feedback opinion views of the respondents

	<i>Could you share your opinion with regard to the experiences, support, feedback you received from your supervisors during the report writing?</i>	<i>Your opinion to other students, respondent 1 explains</i>
Respondent 1	"Report writing was initially very tough. But after the supervision of my teacher, I found the importance of supervisor. He patiently corrected all my mistakes and told me what would make my thesis more convenient and reliable. He was really supportive and looked after each and every student, he gave us the time needed and was very happy with the progress made".	"I would like to tell that thesis writing is not very tough with the right kind of feedback and guidance. So always seek for right guider and follow the instructions correctly".
Respondent 5	"Since this was my first ever report writing, I feel like I had a really good support from my supervisor. He personally gave each and every student the time that was required to complete the thesis and moreover he was patient with us. He detailedly read all my writings and amended the mistakes. Overall, my experience while doing the thesis was really good and effective. Adding I would like to thank supervisor sir for providing such a terrific guidance".	"What I would like to tell is that do not procrastinate while doing the thesis because at first it might look like thesis is child's play it actually is not. It requires a lot of time, hard work, persistency as well as a lot of mistakes to make a good thesis".
Respondent 7	"In the beginning, I felt the pressure on us was quite hectic, but with time as we put hard-work and time on the report the results were fruitful. I learnt how to conduct questionnaire, learnt use of Google docs etc. The best part of the process was the supervision by you, where you were not only leaving pressure on our shoulder but you yourself were working hard with us. Also, not only me, but all members of our group were quite determined and hardworking which implies it was your pathway, your supervision that led us to the success that we have achieved today. Lastly, I'm very grateful that you were my/our supervisor".	"Generally, I believe, all the students have put their time and effort in their respective report, but if talking about our group I felt we were the best as all of us were really indulge to our report and your guidelines. With due respect to all the other supervisor and fellow friends, I firmly believe that we were the best group and we had the opportunity to learn from the best".
Respondent 9	"I was very pleased to have sir as my supervisor due to which I have completed by research on time. I have continuously got support from him. As he was easily accessible to us both via virtually and physically, we have conducted various meeting and discussion at my different stage of report writing. He used to guide us sequentially i.e progressing for the completion of the report writing Chapter wise Chapter. We used to submit him soft copies prepared report on which he used to provide us his valuable comments and feedback. Incorporating this comments and feedbacks we have successfully completed our research work".	"The research work is very helpful us, it will help us to develop our various skills and capacities like report writing, public speaking, collecting data and analyzing it to get the specific results for the research that we have conducted. Thus in my opinion each of the individual must be sincere while working on report writing for research work".
Respondent 10	"The report writing would not have been completed without the guidance of my supervisor. From the beginning of the report to the questionnaire and to the conclusion, the advice, feedback and support from the supervisor was crucial. I would like to once again appreciate and convey my gratitude to Mani sir for his dedicated supervision".	"Research report is a crucial part of the completion of BBS program and thus every student must take this seriously as we get to learn a lot of things and gain experiences in the field and within the overall process".

Individuals are different Bateson (2015), Plaks, Levy, & Dweck, (2009), Plomin & Daniels (1987) and all individuals have different commitment levels. The commitment level is also directed by their personality, psychological paradigm of understanding and grasping the ideas. The exchange of ideas and thought with regards to scientific writing to academic standard has a transformational paradigm and yet it can take some time for everyone to grasp the ideas at once. Hazi (2020) indicates that students are considered as a passive recipient and their responses are taken too generic to promote teaching and its improvement.

However, supervision and teaching are not understandably the same, taking these two as synonyms; it can create additional variations between the supervisors and the students. This can create a vibration between their attitudinal and behavioural commitments. This stage is however the pivotal point to enhance the Collision of Acceptance (CoA) by understanding the level of open source and close source understanding of the students (Figure 1).

The illustration in figure 2 shows how the level of behavioural commitment (CSU) increases but the attitudinal (OSU) is corroborating with the stagnant growth and is not declining. It can however, increase if

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the students are writing the academic report continuously. The stagnant growth of the attitudinal (OSU) can have impact on development of skills, ability, knowledge, competences and intelligence (SAKCI) towards academic writing in future. Alike psychological paradigm, the personality can also have an immense impact on shaping their commitment level, which can be understood by the *Collision of Ignorance (CoI)* stage. This stage is about becoming overconfident and assuming that the completion of one academic report could be replicated but it is however, not as it can be assumed as. Academic writing may be assumed as similar formation pattern but every work is different and can require various levels of SAKCI.

Theoretical Findings vs. Theoretical assumptions

Theoretical framework to rethink education is important to practice hand-on application for improving students learning outcomes. This rethinking of education through the theoretical lens can generate transformation of education to students while supervision is used as a transformative tool towards learning (Matte, 2020). This can further generate additional commitment level amongst students.

The reoccurrence commitment level in students can have impact through the Collision of Ignorance. The level of commitments depends on the higher and the lower side of Collision of Ignorance stages. The higher level of collision of ignorance, the behavioural commitment (Close source understanding) can increase, whereas the lower level of Collision of Ignorance, the attitudinal commitment (Open source understanding) is increased. However, the open source and close source understanding is not mutually exclusive and can increase and decrease which also depends upon the individual's personality.

The Collision of Acceptance (CoA) and Collision of Ignorance (CoI) are two levels of commitment that can generate disorientation and can create personality misrepresentation between both the supervisors and the students. However, these collisions are essential to shape the behavioural pattern of both the supervisors and the students. These collision is necessary to understand the level of personality crisis, which help to support to develop the open source understanding (attitudinal commitment) in students.

However, Collision of Ignorance (CoI) is important to develop further towards shaping OSU but this however can take a flight to different directions and rebuilt the CSU (Behavioural commitment). Although, CSU is not desirable in many instances, the passing through of CoI can regenerate the OSU (attitudinal commitment) in simpler form without having passed through the Collision of Acceptance (CoA) again.

Within the theoretical framework, the theoretical assumptions entails to organizational performances directly connected with individuals/groups commitment level. However the theoretical finding suggests that commitment is directly connected with individuals' personality and their styles and approaches.

Figure 3 Theoretical findings on commitment with personality and styles

In the figure 3, the CoA and CoI are shaped according to the individual's personality and their styles and approaches. There can be a various attributes that defines personality and styles. According to Yeigh (2020) in recent time context and personality have changed within the teachers and students. Although the personality study was not the core area of this study, it was understood that while studying the student's behavioural and attitudinal commitment personality and their styles/approached were observed and monitored during the CoA and CoI stages. The observation and monitoring were conducted by the few people who were constantly visiting my office during the supervision period with students and they were also asked to give feedback of the students on the post behavioural progress during and after the report writing.

While the theoretical assumptions are not incorrect, it contains multiple micros attributes that constantly are connecting to individuals' commitment level. These micros attributes also plays pivotal roles in shaping the behavioural pattern and therefore instigate towards increase or decrease of OSU and CSU. These micros attributes are rolling on within the paradigm of individuals' personality and styles. Moreover, these personality and styles are either coming through nature or nurture and through both of these ways, it can impact on the behavioural aspects of an individuals', this thus can further shape the commitment level, nevertheless, the external environments such as pandemic related to COVID 19 insurgency and lockdown can further shape their behavioural intentions.

Nevertheless, the environment forces such as academic pressures, supervisors accountability, peer pressures so on and so forth can also be a vital components to increase the OSU (attitudinal commitment), however, this could be nurtured, which can be time bound and soon after the environmental forces settle down to release low pressure, the OSU does have a tendencies to decrease. However, CSU (behavioural commitment) can be nature based and have engraved into individuals personality and styles which can be long lasting, thus can decrease with external pressures but can increase to gain as according to the external pressures is released. Therefore, it can be suggested that motivation to achieve certain goal can increase the attitudinal

commitment (OSU) but may decrease overtime. It can also be entailed that OSU can be regenerated through the moderate stress or pressure from the environment on a constant and consistency level.

Conclusion

Commitments of any form exist in all individuals during the tenure of work in any organization. The essential form of commitment that organization need is the OSU (attitudinal commitment), however, individuals always have the tendencies to reflect the CSU (behavioural commitment), which is not desired by any organization. Personality can change, likewise, the commitment level of individuals also changes and can be changed through the pressure of external environments. Although, commitment is a separate component of human nature, the attributes of personality and styles have tendencies to deflect into commitment level thus, it instigates to drive the commitment level either by increasing or decreasing the commitment transformation in an individual. The corrective measures to enhance commitment need to come from both the supervisor and the students while it is also necessary for both the individuals to come into the (CoA) level. This further instigates the trigger to enhance the OSC to standard level of acceptance. While OSC is a time bound commitment and is nurtured, CSU is a behavioural outcome and is naturally acquired and can have a longer sustainability. Finally, although, both these OSU and CSU have the environmental impact, it can be both nurtured and shaped through the implication of moderate stress through the environmental forces.

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